

Influence of African Traditional Beliefs and Practices on Healthcare Utilisation in Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the enduring influence of African traditional beliefs and practices on healthcare utilisation in Anambra State, Nigeria. Despite the availability of modern health facilities, many people in the region still interpret illness through spiritual and cultural lenses, including ancestral displeasure, witchcraft, and supernatural forces. The research investigated how these beliefs affect decisions about when, where, and from whom to seek medical help. A multistage cross-sectional research design was adopted, utilizing quantitative and qualitative approaches. Data were collected through semi-structured questionnaires administered to healthcare professionals and members of the public, as well as in-depth interviews with traditional healers, medical practitioners, and patients. Secondary sources, including journal articles, government documents, health reports, and other relevant literature, were also consulted to provide theoretical and empirical support for the study. The study shows that traditional explanations of illness often guide initial treatment choices, leading many to consult traditional healers, herbalists, or spiritualists before or alongside orthodox medical services. Factors such as the perceived nature of the illness, age, and level of education appear to affect these choices. The findings highlight that while traditional practices offer emotional and cultural comfort, they sometimes cause delays in seeking timely biomedical care. The study concludes that any meaningful improvement in healthcare utilisation in Anambra State must involve culturally sensitive integration of both traditional and modern systems rather than outright replacement of one with the other.

Keywords: Africa traditional medical; belief; cultural practices; healthcare; culture.

Pengaruh Kepercayaan dan Praktik Tradisional Afrika terhadap Pemanfaatan Layanan Kesehatan di Negara Bagian Anambra, Nigeria

Abstrak

Penelitian ini mengkaji pengaruh yang terus bertahan dari kepercayaan dan praktik tradisional Afrika terhadap pemanfaatan layanan kesehatan di Negara Bagian Anambra, Nigeria. Meskipun fasilitas kesehatan modern tersedia, banyak masyarakat di wilayah tersebut masih menafsirkan penyakit melalui perspektif spiritual dan budaya, termasuk ketidaksenangan leluhur, sihir, dan kekuatan supranatural. Penelitian ini menyelidiki bagaimana kepercayaan tersebut memengaruhi keputusan mengenai kapan, di mana, dan kepada siapa seseorang mencari bantuan medis. Penelitian ini menggunakan desain penelitian potong lintang (cross-sectional) bertahap (multistage) dengan pendekatan kuantitatif dan kualitatif. Data dikumpulkan melalui kuesioner semi-terstruktur yang diberikan kepada tenaga kesehatan dan anggota masyarakat, serta wawancara mendalam dengan tabib tradisional, praktisi medis, dan pasien. Sumber data sekunder, termasuk artikel jurnal, dokumen pemerintah, laporan kesehatan, dan literatur relevan lainnya, juga digunakan untuk memberikan dukungan teoretis dan empiris bagi penelitian ini. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa penjelasan tradisional mengenai penyakit sering kali menjadi dasar pilihan pengobatan awal, sehingga banyak orang lebih memilih berkonsultasi dengan tabib tradisional, herbalis, atau pemuka spiritual sebelum atau bersamaan dengan memanfaatkan layanan medis modern. Faktor-faktor seperti persepsi terhadap jenis penyakit, usia, dan tingkat pendidikan tampaknya memengaruhi pilihan tersebut. Temuan penelitian menegaskan bahwa meskipun praktik tradisional memberikan kenyamanan emosional dan budaya, praktik tersebut terkadang menyebabkan keterlambatan dalam memperoleh layanan kesehatan.

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biomedis yang tepat waktu. Penelitian ini menyimpulkan bahwa setiap upaya yang bermakna untuk meningkatkan pemanfaatan layanan kesehatan di Negara Bagian Anambra harus melibatkan integrasi yang sensitif terhadap budaya antara sistem kesehatan tradisional dan modern, bukan menggantikan salah satunya secara sepihak.

Kata kunci: pengobatan tradisional Afrika; kepercayaan; praktik budaya; layanan kesehatan; budaya.

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INTRODUCTION

African societies and their cultural practices have over the years drawn global focus when it comes to the health conditions of the people. Tambo (2014) observes that, across much of Africa, cultural beliefs, religion, and traditional medicines have long walked together, increasingly clashing with modern healthcare. Tambo notes that it is estimated that about 70-80% of the population in developing countries relies on traditional medicine for their health care needs. In spite of evidence from studies showing positive outcomes linked to traditional medicine, concerns about complications, lack of standardization, and sweeping claims of universal efficacy in treating illnesses have led to more deaths among rural residents, who are known to be among the higher users of traditional medicine.

Numerous investigations into African traditional beliefs and practices and healthcare utilization have been carried out across diverse tradition (Kagawa-Singer & Kassim-Lakha, 2013; Betancourt et al., 2013; Smedley et al., 2015; Suarez et al., 2015; Okoronkwo et al., 2019). Some scholars contend that African traditional beliefs and practices influences shape patterns of healthcare consumption, noting that many civilizations employ traditional or alternative medicine, sometimes alongside Western treatment referred to as modern healthcare. Moreover, studies such as Gee et al. (2015) indicate that ethnic and cultural groups use healthcare in distinct ways.

Traditional healing embodies the African view of health and the method by which healing is pursued. Modern healing and medicine trace their roots to these traditional practices, existing well before scientific and technological advances entered medicinal work. Yet the traditional healing system remains deeply woven into cultural life, representing a diverse mix of indigenous, unconventional, and folk medical methods that are loosely joined by a shared reliance on empirical observation or non-scientific approaches to the broader challenge of healing and health care. (Anfom, 1986).

In Africa, ill health is anything that jeopardizes a fuller life; thus, healing in traditional African societies is the act of restoring life to its fullness. It concerns the spiritual, social, and mental well-being of a person, particularly the harmony of the entire human being. Consequently, the idea of healing is deeply linked to the African view of the cosmos and the notion of man.

Consensus in public health and health communication acknowledges the significant role of African traditional beliefs and practices as a factor linked to health and health behaviors (Institute of Medicine, Kreuter and McClure, 2004). Consequently, health communication is defined as the study and practice of conveying promotional health information through public health campaigns, health education, and interactions between doctors and patients (Abroms & Maibach, 2008). A central aim of health communication is to foster health literacy in patients, empowering them to make informed health decisions. This is why Edgar and Hyde (2004) advocate interpersonal engagement between healthcare professionals and patients as among the most potent approaches for securing positive health outcomes in patients. Frank, Jerrant, Fiscella, Shields, Tancredi, and Epstein (2006) corroborate this stance by asserting that effective communication between physicians and their patients has been linked to patient

outcomes, and in Fong's (2010) words, the patient's health outcome stands as the ultimate aim of healthcare provider-patient communication.

Research indicates that the pursuit of effective communication between healthcare providers and their patients has long wrestled with a number of barriers, one of which is patients' cultural health beliefs (Diette & Rand, 2007; Tongue Epps & Forese, 2005). Zhumadilora (2013) terms this miscommunication, arising from mismatches in expectations between healthcare professionals and patients due to cultural and historical differences. That situation sparked the idea of African traditional beliefs and practices competence. Korez- vilde (2016) defines cultural competence as the ability of someone from one traditional belief to engage effectively with individuals from another culture. Echoing Betancourt and Langer in Betancourt et al (2015), when healthcare providers overlook socio-cultural differences between themselves and their patients, communication and trust can falter. This can result in patient dissatisfaction, poorer adherence to medications and health-promoting strategies, and worse health outcomes. Put differently, the field of cultural competence in healthcare has formed to realize the overarching aim of a healthcare system and workforce capable of delivering the highest quality of care to every patient, regardless of race, ethnicity, cultural background, or English proficiency (Betancourt et al., 2002).

Intriguingly, contrary to the prior arguments and concerns raised about the African traditional belief and practices implications of patient/provider communication for the quality of healthcare delivery, Ojua in Ojua et al. (2013) and Katung (2001) contend that development, civilization, education, and other factors have fostered substantial positive shifts in Africans' beliefs and conduct toward patronage of allopathic medicine. How valid is this claim? To establish certainty, it became essential to empirically test the impact of cultural health beliefs on the communication between healthcare providers and patients at primary healthcare centers in Anambra State, as well as how these beliefs shape patients' medication adherence and their patterns of seeking healthcare.

African traditional beliefs and practices, a socially conveyed system of shared knowledge, beliefs and/or practices that differs across groups and among individuals within those groups, has long served as a vital mode of adaptation in human history. Cultural norms and values, transmitted through generations, can shape lifestyle choices, dietary patterns, and even the way aging is perceived (Achen, Atekyereza & Rwabukwali, 2021). Put simply, the impact of social and cultural factors on health encompasses both temporal dimensions key life-course stages and the effects of accumulated exposure and spatial dimensions multiple levels of exposure. The settings in which African traditional beliefs and practices factors act to influence health outcomes are referred to as the cultural environment (Hernandez & Gibb, 2019).

Lately, researchers in sociology and social epidemiology have directed focus toward an expanding set of African traditional beliefs and practices factors as precursors to health. These factors encompass acculturation, social deprivation, social networks and support, and the psychosocial workplace climate, along with broader traits of social settings such as income distribution, social cohesion, social capital, and collective efficacy (Hernandez & Gibb, 2019).

Grasping African traditional beliefs and practices nuances is essential for customizing healthcare strategies and support systems to more effectively serve the varied needs of elderly populations across the globe. This intricate matter spans a wide spectrum of cultural dimensions, from long-standing beliefs and practices to socio-economic factors that mold perceptions and responses to illness and well-being in old age.

African traditional beliefs and practices diversity profoundly shapes how communities understand health and disease, influencing their reactions to illnesses and their paths to wellness. African traditional beliefs and practices frequently guide health-seeking behaviors and the use of healthcare

services among seniors. For example, certain cultural groups may emphasize holistic approaches that blend traditional remedies with modern medicine, while others may rely predominantly on conventional medical treatments.

METHODOLOGY

This study made use of a multistage cross-sectional research design to investigate the phenomenon of medical pluralism and healthcare-seeking behavior of the population in Anambra State, Nigeria. It was carried out in selected health facilities and communities within the state to explore how people integrate different systems of health care delivery to satisfy their health requirements.

Information was gathered through the use of a semi-structured questionnaire administered to healthcare professionals and some members of the public. Furthermore, in-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted with carefully selected respondents consisting of traditional healers, medical practitioners, and patients among others.

Secondary data, such as textbooks, journal articles, government documents, health reports, and other research conducted regarding medical pluralism, healthcare seeking behavior, and primary healthcare services in Nigeria were used in this study. They offered both theoretical and empirical information for this study.

Using quantitative, qualitative, and secondary data helped to incorporate statistical trends and personal experiences in regards to healthcare and medical pluralism in Nigeria.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

African traditional beliefs and practices in Anambra State

The practice of medical pluralism remains very common across both rural and urban communities in Anambra State. Most people do not see traditional and modern healthcare as opposites but as complementary systems. A person may visit a hospital for diagnosis or surgery while still consulting a traditional healer for spiritual cleansing or herbal treatment to address the “root cause” of the problem. This dual approach provides emotional and psychological comfort, as traditional practices offer explanations that align with the people’s worldview. However, it can also lead to confusion, conflicting treatments, and sometimes dangerous delays when serious medical conditions are not addressed promptly.

Traditional beliefs particularly influence healthcare decisions for certain types of illnesses. Reproductive health problems, chronic diseases, epilepsy, and mental disorders are widely regarded as having spiritual dimensions. Families often believe that orthodox medicine alone cannot cure these conditions and that rituals, sacrifices, or herbal mixtures are necessary. As a result, many patients only turn to hospitals when traditional methods fail or when the condition becomes life-threatening. This pattern contributes to late presentation of cases at health facilities and affects overall treatment outcomes.

Socio-cultural factors such as respect for elders, fear of social stigma, and loyalty to ancestral traditions further strengthen the influence of these beliefs. Openly rejecting traditional practices can be seen as a betrayal of family and community values. Many individuals therefore continue to use traditional medicine even when they have access to modern healthcare services. This cultural pressure makes it difficult for purely biomedical approaches to gain full acceptance in the region.

For sustainable improvement in healthcare utilisation, there is a clear need to move beyond simply promoting modern medicine. Health planners and practitioners must recognise and respectfully engage with traditional beliefs and healers. Integrating selected aspects of traditional practices into the formal health system, training health workers to be culturally sensitive, and creating dialogue between

both systems could reduce delays in treatment, build trust, and ultimately lead to better health outcomes for the people of Anambra State.

African traditional beliefs and practices - Health Dialogue and the Elderly

African traditional beliefs and practices knowledge passed through communities helps shape a distinct set of health behaviors in older adults. Grasping how beliefs practices are shared between generations is essential to understanding the varied ways diseases and wellness are approached within elderly groups. Socio-economic factors intensify the complexity of this issue. Differences in access to healthcare, education, and financial means influence the health outcomes and responses of older individuals. Vulnerable populations facing economic hardship may struggle to obtain suitable medical care, resulting in delayed interventions and reduced well-being (Wee, Yeo, Yang & Hannan, 2012). The high prevalence of chronic illnesses among the elderly adds another layer to the challenge. As cultures shift, so do the illnesses that touch older generations. Chronic conditions like diabetes, heart disease, and neurodegenerative disorders demand ongoing management and care. The African traditional beliefs and practices framework through which these conditions are viewed shapes how faithfully the elderly follow treatment plans and adopt lifestyle changes. Attitudes toward aging within a culture add layers of complexity to the issue. In some societies, aging is honored and linked to wisdom, fostering proactive health-seeking behaviors. In others, where aging carries stigma, older individuals may be reluctant to seek medical help or participate in preventive health practices. Grasping these African traditional beliefs and practices subtleties is crucial for crafting effective approaches to promote healthy aging (Hernandez & Gibb, 2019).

Moreover, the influence of globalization on African traditional beliefs and practices values and practices remains undeniable. Migration and African traditional beliefs and practices assimilation may give rise to a hybridization of health beliefs and behaviors among older adults. This dynamic interaction between traditional and adopted African traditional beliefs and practices elements forges a distinctive setting that informs responses to illness and wellness.

African traditional beliefs and practices Orientations linked to Illness and Wellness

Rosén (2015) explored how African traditional beliefs and practices factors shape the prevalence of overweight and obesity among adults in Babati town, Tanzania. A qualitative field study in Babati was carried out in February and March 2014 to collect information and discern how African traditional beliefs and practices shapes health perceptions and practices. In this research, the PEN-3 African traditional beliefs and practices model served as the theoretical framework to uncover the underlying causes driving a specific behavior and action.

The study also revealed that attitudes, knowledge, and perceptions bear a far greater influence. Being overweight is often tied to notions of wealth and health; this drives many to pursue that ideal, for both men and women. Once more, the study showed that culture plays a substantial role, since everything people do and every choice they make can be linked to their traditional belief belonging, the ideals they strive for, their food selections, views on physical activity, and risk perceptions regarding illness. Consequently, the study concludes that culture cannot be disregarded in health interventions.

African traditional beliefs and practices, Religion and Health Care, Nigeria

As a secular nation, Nigeria's constitution ensures freedom of worship. Consequently, a multitude of faiths flourish across the country. Christians largely inhabit the southern regions South West, South-South, and South East while Muslims are mainly concentrated in the north. Indigenous faiths, rooted in belief in deities, spirits, and ancestral reverence, are scattered across the nation.

Many Muslims and Christians there also blend their faith with more unorthodox, native beliefs. Nigeria holds Africa's largest population, boasting over 250 ethnic groups and more than 510 languages. This has crafted a nation of striking complexity, with varied African traditional beliefs and practices and religious practices that shape how people in the same country view and handle health matters. Extended families remain the norm and, in fact, constitute the backbone of Nigerian social life. Grandparents, cousins, aunts, uncles, sisters, brothers, and in-laws all move through life as a unit. Family ties are governed by hierarchy and seniority (Familismo). Individuals seek financial help and guidance from members of the extended family, and the family is expected to look after the welfare of every member, even in times of illness.

Thus, the person who gains from the family frame is anticipated to owe loyalty to the system in return and, in certain circumstances, lacks the autonomy to determine health matters without the family's input. Yet, in many urban spaces today, with the spread of western culture, the influence of the extended family structure is gradually waning, though a robust tradition of mutual care and accountability among members endures.

The health care systems in Nigeria and many African nations grew out of colonial medical services that prioritized costly, high-tech, urban-focused, curative care. When independence arrived in 1960, Nigeria inherited health care structures modeled after those of industrialized Western powers that had colonized them. Public health initiatives from international development agencies during that era were largely aimed at eradicating particular diseases such as smallpox, yaws, and malaria. Each disease eradication program operated on its own, with separate administration and budgets, and with minimal integration into the broader health system.

There were certain gains in this era, such as the eradication of smallpox, chickenpox, and yaws. Yet these short-term efforts did not tackle the overall disease burden faced by the poor populations. The situation deteriorated into the early 1970s as populations grew and health outcomes continued to fail, prompting health policy changes and the rise of the Alma Ata Declaration in 1978, with Nigeria adopting PHC as the core of its national health policy from 1988 onward.

Health Seeking Behavior and the Influence of African traditional beliefs and practices

A range of factors shapes how individuals pursue health, including predisposing variables such as age, sex, culture, religion, occupation, past illness experiences, education level, general attitudes toward health services, and knowledge of the presenting illness. Enabling factors also matter—availability of health services, financial means, social networks and support, and perceptions of disease severity. Behaviors cannot be inferred from any single factor or small set of factors alone. For instance, a practice might align with an etiological understanding, yet in illness models etiologies frequently carry moral weight that infuses meaning into behavior. Pinpointing the key determinants of health-seeking behavior proves useful for guiding health policy interventions.

To truly grasp behaviours, these three factors must be placed in context. Studies of health-seeking behaviour recognize that health control tools, when available, are often underused or used inadequately. Understanding human behaviour is a prerequisite for changing it and for improving health practices. Experts in health interventions and health policy have grown more aware of human behavioural factors in delivering quality health care, a dynamic in Africa frequently shaped by culture. To address community perspectives and needs, health systems must tailor their strategies, incorporating insights from the community's cultural disposition, which in some cases may be anchored in behavioural studies. Culture and personal beliefs exert a crucial influence on health-seeking behaviour, especially in rural areas. Some

hold that the majority of health issues are of a spiritual nature and thus do not warrant the attention of orthodox medicine.

This view is not unique to the Nigerian context; in Tanzania, for instance, Hausmann-Muela et al. describe how malaria and witchcraft can intertwine in illness interpretations. They note that among the Tanzanian populace, the belief that witchcraft can obstruct biomedical treatment or prevent malaria parasites from being detected in the blood arises from the idea that witchcraft casts a veil between the body and the external world, hindering the parasites' revelation. These examples illustrate, sadly, how concepts from different knowledge streams can fuse and generate new, syncretistic readings rather than how new knowledge would supplant existing notions.

Review of Literature on African traditional beliefs and practices

Belief represents a group's shared values, customs, and actions. It encompasses religion, morality, ethics, and social values. Ogunyemi (2018) observed that many indigenous cultures hold to the idea of the interconnectedness of all living beings and the obligation to live in harmony with nature. Nikiforova and Voronova (2023) highlight through their study that cultural belief centers on how groups and cultures form identities, values, and standards. Cultural belief practices include numerous rituals, conventions, and traditions passed down across generations. Such behaviors knit society together and shape a sense of identity. Religion, art, language, and social interactions permeate daily life, reflecting a community's faith, history, and worldview (Salmorin and Gepty, 2023). Belief ideas mold how people perceive, interpret, act, and understand morality, identity, and social duties.

Belief is a intricate and layered idea, embracing a broad spectrum of elements beliefs, customs, language, traditions, arts, and values that a specific group of people shares. It molds how individuals view the world and guides their behaviors, interactions, and social structures (Little & McGivern, 2014). In *Sociology and Anthropology*, Edward Burnett Taylor offered a widely accepted definition in 1871, describing culture as a complex whole comprising knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, custom, and any other abilities and habits learned by a person as a member of society. Across history, diverse cultures have emerged and transformed in different regions, each with its own distinct traits and expressions. On a continental scale, culture unfolds among many communities, illustrating how uniquely it can manifest across places and peoples.

Belief ideas mold how individuals perceive, interpret, act, and grasp morality, identity, and social duties. Belief relativists argue that grasping concepts and actions within a culture matters more than judging them from outside (Eche, 2023), contesting the notion of a universal human morality.

South America stands out for its rich cultural heritage shaped by both indigenous civilizations such as the Inca, Maya, and Aztec and the influences of colonial powers like Spain and Portugal. Across much of the continent, indigenous healing practices persist alongside modern healthcare, with traditional remedies, shamanic ceremonies, and plant-based medicines commonly used to treat health concerns (Reynolds, 2021). In Australia, indigenous cultures, often called Aboriginal or Torres Strait Islander peoples, are among the world's oldest surviving traditions. They are defined by a profound bond with the land, spiritual beliefs, and oral histories carried forward through generations. Indigenous communities in Australia and Pacific Island nations maintain their own traditional healing practices, which may involve herbal medicine, storytelling, and a deep connection to the land.

Moreover, belief notions can shape people's self-perception and identity. Many indigenous communities rely on storytelling and oral traditions to safeguard and pass on history and knowledge (Bordoloi, 2015). These narratives impart life lessons and foster a sense of ancestral belonging. Such practices typically reinforce continuity and belonging, though these effects may differ across cultures. Diwali, the Hindu festival of lights, honors virtue over vice (Yu, & Stoet, 2019). Healthcare utilization

describes the extent to which individuals use health services to maintain their well-being. This concept holds significance for public health and for how healthcare systems function. Personal characteristics, problems within the healthcare system, and socioeconomic factors influence when and how people seek, use, and decide about care. It encompasses health promotion, ongoing maintenance, and medical remediation, and is vital to civilization. Numerous activities, services, and infrastructures contribute to health improvement and disease prevention (World Health Organization, 2015). Access to healthcare is a fundamental human right that benefits both individuals and society.

Davis et al. (2014) observed that numerous industrialized nations' health systems deliver a wide range of services and cutting-edge technologies to both public and private sectors. These systems typically integrate primary care, professional medical services, hospitals, and public health activities to ensure universal access to healthcare. The healthcare utilization model, a core element of healthcare usage, clarifies the factors shaping individuals' medical care decisions. Ronald Andersen's (1968) behavioral model of healthcare utilization identifies three categories of characteristics that influence healthcare use: predisposing variables, such as demographics and attitudes; enabling aspects, including access to care; and need factors, encompassing health conditions. The Abel (2023) model has been widely employed to examine demographic patterns of healthcare consumption.

In addition, planning for healthcare and the distribution of resources hinge on how services are used. Healthcare systems can enhance how resources are allocated, planned, and how access disparities are addressed through deeper utilization analysis. Data informs researchers and policymakers as they map out infrastructure, staffing, and budgets. Regulations and procedures in healthcare influence the availability of medical care. System configurations can vary substantially from one country to another. Canadians with Medicare and other universal health programs are entitled to medical care regardless of income (Koumpouros, 2023). There is scholarly work that investigates factors shaping healthcare utilization. For example, Moonpanane et al. (2022) carried out a study to understand healthcare service use among hill tribe children in underserved communities in Thailand. The study identified access barriers as the central theme.

A further study by Kota et al. (2023) showed that maternal healthcare services have a significant influence on pregnancy and delivery outcomes. Togo, along with other sub-Saharan African nations, faces a public health crisis marked by high maternal and neonatal mortality. This research explored how 15–49-year-old Togolese women utilize maternal health care. The data came from Togo's 2013 Demographic and Health Survey, the country's third such survey. About 4,631 women aged 15–49 were assessed and analyzed.

The outcome criteria included hospital births, adequate prenatal care (ANC) visits, and timely initiation of ANC. The analysis employed Stata 16. The majority of births occurred in health facilities, with 59.99% taking place during appropriate antenatal care (ANC) visits and 27.53% during timely first ANC visits.

The study showed that women in the top wealth quintile were more likely than those in the bottom quintile to initiate their first antenatal care visit at the recommended time, to receive adequate prenatal care, and to deliver in a health facility (OR = 8.53, 95% CI = 4.06, 17.92). Women holding a bachelor's degree or higher were more prone to have timely first antenatal care visits (OR = 1.37, 95% CI = 1.11, 1.69) and to attend a sufficient number of ANC visits (OR = 1.73, 95% CI = 1.42, 2.12). In contrast, rural communities with stronger egalitarianism and indigenous values used healthcare less. Togo noted that sociocultural barriers and socioeconomic disparities influence maternal healthcare usage. Yet, aside from Sibeudu et al. (2019) on immunization utilization, there is a lack of empirical data on how cultural beliefs shape healthcare utilization in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Other topics touched on distance considerations, education and poverty, cultural insensitivity, communication difficulties, tradition, beliefs, and variations in cultural practice, scarcity of child health professionals, and bureaucratic obstacles. In a separate study, Alwan et al (2020) explored the beliefs, perceptions, and behaviors that shape healthcare utilization among Syrian refugee children. The research highlighted four prominent themes: stressors that deter health-seeking behaviors, parental perceptions of health barriers, parental dissatisfaction with the healthcare system, and parental reliance on resilience strategies to overcome obstacles. Stressors encompassed substandard housing and neighborhoods, re-experiencing traumatic events, depression and anxiety, and social isolation. Dissatisfaction encompassed emergency department wait times and limited access to testing and prescriptions. Health barriers included missed appointments, transportation challenges, translation services, health literacy, and care coordination.

Also, Herwansyah et al (2022) in their examination of the use of maternal health services within primary healthcare settings across Southeast Asian countries identified several themes. These encompass cultural and socioeconomic factors, elements linked to the low utilization of ANC, determinants shaping place of delivery and the choice of delivery assistance. Sociocultural barriers and disparities in the provision of health services emerge as the primary factors tied to underuse of these services. Mochache et al (2020) found that religious and socio-cultural norms, together with gender stereotypes, significantly influence the uptake and use of maternal health services, including facility-based delivery and contraception. A notable point was the unspoken deference to the guidance of a prominent matriarchal figure in the decision-making process.

Findings:

The results indicated the low utilization of the primary health care system in Anambra State based on the cultural beliefs and perceptions regarding disease causation. Most of the respondents indicated that some illnesses are caused by supernatural powers, witchcraft, angry gods, and spiritual attacks from their neighbors. This led to many people preferring traditional treatments and healing through religion rather than conventional treatments.

The results indicated that cultural and religious beliefs have a huge impact on the concept of medical pluralism because some people use the services of traditional healers along with those of the conventional system while others depend only on the traditional healers and spiritualists who have the ability to treat physical as well as spiritual diseases.

In summary, African traditional beliefs and practices stands as a dynamic and intricate force that molds human societies in deep, worldwide ways. African traditional beliefs and practices also shapes health habits and approaches to resolving health-related challenges. From the enduring traditions of Indigenous communities to the cutting-edge innovations of interconnected societies, culture covers a broad spectrum of beliefs, customs, and expressions that enrich the tapestry of human experience. Consequently, how illness is addressed within a community or among people can be influenced and guided by their cultural framework.

CONCLUSION

This study has clearly demonstrated that African traditional beliefs and practices continue to exert a strong influence on healthcare utilisation patterns in Anambra State, Nigeria. Despite the presence of modern health facilities, many people still interpret illness through a spiritual and cultural lens, often shaping their choice of treatment and the sequence in which they seek care. The persistent belief in supernatural causation of diseases, the role of ancestors, and the perceived efficacy of traditional medicine

have sustained a system of medical pluralism where traditional and orthodox healthcare coexist, sometimes in harmony and at other times in tension.

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